

FEMINIST ACTIVISM AND SOCIAL MEDIA: A STUDY OF GENDER EQUALITY CAMPAIGN IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study examined the role of social media in feminist activism and gender equality campaigns in Nigeria, focusing on the perception of Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria residents. Anchored on feminist theory, social movement theory, and media ecology theory, the study adopted Survey method. Out of the 360,268 population of the study, 400 serves as the sample size. Findings show that residents primarily use Twitter and WhatsApp, encountering gender equality campaigns monthly and engaging with them mostly by liking posts. The study reveals that social media effectively raises awareness about gender equality issues and addresses key challenges such as gender-based violence, women's political participation, economic empowerment, and cultural stereotypes. Respondents believe that online campaigns translate into real-life change, highlighting their potential for tangible impact. However, barriers such as online harassment, digital illiteracy, and cultural resistance were identified, while issues like internet inaccessibility and lack of engagement were not considered major challenges. To enhance effectiveness, respondents agree to collaborating with influencers, using local languages, educating the public, and integrating online and offline activism. This study recommends that the Nigeria government should incorporate digital literacy training into national education initiatives, prioritizing women's empowerment and enabling them to effectively engage with feminist campaigns. Organisations and organisers of feminist campaign and movement should provide resources and support for feminist campaigns to incorporate local languages, ensuring that messages are accessible and culturally relevant to diverse populations.*

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Introduction

In recent years, social media has emerged as a tool for advancing feminist activism and gender equality globally. Across Africa, where traditional gender norms and systemic inequalities persist, social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram have become spaces for advocacy, awareness, and mobilization. These platforms have provided feminists with a cost-effective and far-reaching means to amplify their voices, challenge patriarchal systems, and inspire societal change (Mutsvairo & Salgado, 2021).

The fight for gender equality in Africa is deeply rooted in historical struggles against colonialism, traditional patriarchy, and socio-economic disparities. However, the advent of digital technologies has shifted the terrain of activism, enabling grassroots organizations and individuals to bypass traditional gatekeepers of information and directly engage with a global audience (Bosch, 2017). Social media campaigns such as #BringBackOurGirls in Nigeria, #MeToo in South Africa, and #MyDressMyChoice in Kenya exemplify how online activism can spark national and international conversations about gender-based violence, sexual harassment, and women's rights (Ekhator, 2015; Tamale, 2020). The intersection of feminist activism and social media in Africa reveals both opportunities and challenges. On one hand, digital platforms empower activists to create inclusive narratives and mobilize marginalized voices. On the other

hand, online spaces are often fraught with cyberbullying, misogyny, and digital surveillance, which disproportionately affect women activists (Ogola, 2019). Thus, while social media offers a vital space for feminist advocacy, it also mirrors and sometimes exacerbates the systemic inequalities present in offline settings.

This study examines how feminist activists in Africa utilize social media to promote gender equality campaigns. By exploring public perception of gender equality campaigns, this research seeks to illuminate the strategies, successes, and limitations of digital feminist movements in the African continent. Ultimately, the study aims to contribute to the broader discourse on digital activism and gender equity, emphasizing the potential of social media to reshape the fight for justice in Africa.

Statement of the Problem

Despite significant strides in promoting gender equality, Africa continues to grapple with entrenched patriarchal structures and socio-cultural norms that perpetuate gender-based discrimination. Traditional methods of advocacy often fail to reach broader audiences or influence policy effectively. Social media, with its vast reach and interactive features, offers an alternative platform for feminist activism. However, the extent to which African feminist movements have successfully utilized these platforms to achieve tangible outcomes remains underexplored. Additionally, challenges such as online harassment, limited digital literacy, and

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unequal access to technology hinder the efficacy of these campaigns (Ogola, 2019; Mutsvairo & Salgado, 2021). Addressing these gaps is crucial to understanding the role of social media in advancing gender equality in Nigeria and Africa.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the strategies employed by feminist activists in Nigeria to leverage social media for gender equality campaigns.
2. To analyze the impact of social media-based feminist activism on societal attitudes and policy changes in Nigeria.
3. To identify the challenges and limitations faced by feminist activists in utilizing digital platforms for advocacy in Nigeria.

Feminist Activism and Social Media in the Digital Era

The concept of feminist activism has evolved significantly, particularly with the advent of digital platforms. Feminism advocates for gender equality by challenging systemic inequalities, promoting women's rights, and addressing issues such as gender-based violence, political representation, and economic empowerment (Hooks, 2015). In Africa, feminist activism is deeply rooted in the socio-political struggles of colonialism and patriarchy, with digital tools adding a new dimension to advocacy efforts (Tamale, 2020).

Social media, as a concept, represents a technology that fosters communication, engagement, and mobilization across various spheres (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Akinwumi,

Afolabi, Owotogbe & Oladimeji, 2021). Platforms like Twitter and Facebook have become spaces where feminist activists can share information, mobilize support, and initiate grassroots movements (Bosch, 2017). The use of hashtags, such as #BringBackOurGirls, #MeToo, and #SayHerName, highlights how online campaigns can amplify voices and challenge the status quo (Mutsvairo & Salgado, 2021).

Digital feminist activism leverages the accessibility and immediacy of social media to counteract the limitations of traditional activism. According to Tufekci (2017), the internet has enabled marginalized groups to overcome geographical and economic barriers, creating opportunities for collective action. However, the effectiveness of online activism is influenced by socio-cultural contexts, digital literacy, and the availability of technological resources (Ogola, 2019).

In the African context, feminist activists have adapted digital tools to address issues specific to their societies, such as harmful cultural practices, domestic violence, and economic disenfranchisement (Ekhtator, 2015). The use of social media for feminist activism is not merely a replication of Western strategies but reflects unique local challenges and opportunities (Bosch, 2017).

Despite its potential, digital feminist activism faces significant challenges. Cyberbullying, online harassment, and digital surveillance are pervasive issues that disproportionately target

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women activists (Jane, 2014). According to Khamis, Ang, and Welling (2012), the online environment often mirrors offline inequalities, with power dynamics influencing access and participation. In Africa, the digital divide and unequal access to technology further exacerbate these challenges (Chatora, 2012).

Review of Empirical Studies

Feminist activism in Africa has undergone significant transformation with the advent of social media, which serves as a tool for mobilization, engagement, and advocacy. Numerous empirical studies have explored the intersection of digital platforms and gender equality campaigns.

Bosch (2017) analyzed Twitter activism during the #RhodesMustFall movement in South Africa, highlighting how hashtags amplify marginalized voices. Similarly, Tufekci (2017) emphasized the power of networked protests, noting the duality of mobilization and the challenges of sustaining momentum. These studies underscore the role of digital platforms in bypassing traditional media gatekeepers to reach wider audiences.

In Kenya, Ogola (2019) identified the polarizing nature of Twitter discussions, where feminist activists face both support and harassment. Chatora (2012) further argued that while social media fosters activism, cultural resistance and limited digital access hinder its impact in African contexts.

Sohela & Awino (2021): This study analyzes the impact of feminist protests on policy reforms,

highlighting that while the presence of female leaders doesn't automatically result in gender equality policies, active women's movements significantly contribute to policy changes. Jennifer & Julia (2020) discusses how autonomous feminist activism influences progressive social policies, emphasizing that grassroots mobilization is crucial for enacting policy changes that address gender inequalities. Marianna & Alison (2023) reflects on the application of feminist theories and activism within organizational contexts, suggesting that such approaches can address vital societal challenges and influence policy reforms. Weldon & Htun (2013) study finds that feminist activism is the most consistent factor driving policy change to combat violence against women, often playing a more significant role than political party ideologies.

Mutsvairo and Salgado (2021) explored feminist movements across Nigeria, South Africa, and Kenya, revealing the interplay between global strategies and local realities. Tamale (2020) emphasized Afro-feminism's unique approach to leveraging social media to address issues like gender-based violence and economic disenfranchisement.

Ekhatior (2015) and Davis (2016) focused on Nigeria's #BringBackOurGirls campaign, noting its success in raising international awareness but highlighting its limited impact on systemic issues due to weak institutional frameworks. Similarly, Nyabola (2018) examined Kenya's

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#MyDressMyChoice, which challenged societal norms about women's autonomy but struggled with digital exclusion.

Jane (2014) investigated online misogyny, revealing that cyberbullying and harassment often silence feminist voices. Bosch and Chuma (2019) highlighted the privacy benefits of WhatsApp for organizing safe spaces, while Khamis, Ang, and Welling (2012) analyzed how feminist influencers navigate authenticity and backlash in their advocacy.

Theoretical Framework

Feminist activism has witnessed significant transformation with the advent of social media, especially in Africa. This study explores how digital platforms facilitate gender equality campaigns by anchoring the research on three primary theories: feminist theory, social movement theory, and media ecology theory.

Feminist Theory

Feminist theory forms the ideological foundation of this study, addressing the systemic structures that perpetuate gender inequality. It critiques patriarchal systems that marginalize women and other oppressed groups while advocating for change.

Simone de Beauvoir's (1949) work challenged traditional gender roles, while more contemporary scholars like bell hooks (1984) and Chandra Talpade Mohanty (2003) emphasized the intersection of gender with race, class, and cultural identity.

Feminist theory underscores the importance of digital platforms as spaces where marginalized voices can disrupt dominant narratives. Activists use social media to challenge gender stereotypes, advocate for policy changes, and amplify lived experiences often ignored by traditional media (Mohanty, 2003). In the African context, campaigns like #BringBackOurGirls and #MyDressMyChoice illustrate how feminist theory is operationalized in online spaces to foster awareness and drive collective action.

Social Movement Theory

Social movement theory examines the dynamics of collective action, providing insights into the processes through which feminist movements mobilize resources, engage participants, and sustain momentum.

Proponents like Charles Tilly (1978) and Sidney Tarrow (1998) identified the importance of framing, resource mobilization, and the political opportunity structure in sustaining social movements.

Social media has transformed feminist movements by democratizing access to resources and enabling rapid mobilization. Digital campaigns use hashtags, viral content, and virtual communities to create a shared identity among activists. For instance, the #EndFGM campaign leveraged social movement principles to build global networks that advocate against female genital mutilation, combining grassroots efforts with international support.

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However, social movement theory also highlights challenges such as sustaining engagement, countering misinformation, and navigating online harassment, which can undermine digital activism.

Media Ecology Theory

Media ecology theory explores the relationship between communication technologies and societal structures, emphasizing how media shape human interaction and cultural transformation.

Marshall McLuhan (1964) introduced the concept of the "global village," where technology connects diverse groups, while Neil Postman (1985) explored how media environments influence public discourse.

Social media platforms, as extensions of human communication, facilitate real-time interaction and bridge geographical divides. Activists can now reach global audiences, raising awareness of localized issues on an unprecedented scale. For instance, African feminists have used platforms like Twitter and Instagram to highlight gender-based violence and economic inequalities, challenging cultural taboos and fostering dialogue.

Despite its potential, media ecology theory also recognizes the drawbacks of digital activism, such as the digital divide, where limited internet access and digital illiteracy in parts of Africa hinder inclusive participation. Furthermore, the algorithms governing social media platforms often prioritize sensational content,

complicating nuanced discussions about gender equality.

By adopting these theoretical lenses, the research aims to contribute to ongoing discussions about the role of social media in fostering gender equality and addressing systemic barriers to feminist activism in Africa.

Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive research design to explore how feminist activists in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria leverages social media for gender equality campaigns. The target population for this study is the 360,268 residents of Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, a demographic representative of grassroots and urban populations in Africa (Ondobudget.org, 2010). This population of the study was selected by the researcher because it is one of the most populated areas in Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample size is determined using Taro Yamane's formula, the sample size for this study is approximately 400 respondents.

A multi-stage sampling technique is employed to ensure a representative sample. First, the population is stratified based on the 10 districts in the local governments: Igbatoro, Oda, Apomu, Isinkan I, Isinkan II, Ijomu, Lisa, Odopetu, Oke aro I and Oke Aro II. Then, a simple random sampling method is used to 40 participants from each stratum that are familiar with feminist activism on social media. Data were collected through closed and open-ended questionnaires.

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The questionnaires focus on participants' use of social media, perceptions of feminist activism, experiences with online advocacy and insights

into the strategies and challenges faced by activists. The questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools.

Data Presentation and Discussion

Table 1. Awareness and Engagement with Feminist Activism on Social Media

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Which social media platforms do you use the most?		
Facebook	44	11%
Twitter	128	32%
Instagram	20	5%
WhatsApp	126	32%
TikTok	82	20%
Total	400	100%
How often do you encounter gender equality campaigns on social media?		
Daily	-	-
Weekly	36	9%
Monthly	244	61%
Rarely	56	14%
Never	64	16%
Total	400	100%
How did you react to gender equality campaigns on social media?		
Liked posts	17	43%
Share content	105	26%
Joined online discussions	72	18%
Attended offline events via online platforms	52	13%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field work, 2025

The table above shows that majority of the respondents, representing 64% mostly use Twitter or Whatsapp, while the remaining 36% most use one out of Facebook, Instagram and Tiktok. Furthermore, majority of the respondents encounter gender equality campaigns on social media on monthly basis, while Majority (43%) of the respondents react by liking posts on gender equality campaigns on social media.

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The findings from the above table indicate that residents of Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria, predominantly use Twitter and WhatsApp, encounter gender equality campaigns on social media on a monthly basis, and usually react by liking posts on gender equality campaigns. These findings align with Akinwumi et al.'s (2021) study, which identified WhatsApp as the most commonly used social media platform for information dissemination and noted that the public typically reacts to information available on social media.

Table 2. Perceived Impact of Feminist Activism on Social Media

Option	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL
Social media has contributed to increasing awareness of gender equality issues?	223 (56%)	93 (24%)	14 (3%)	53 (13%)	17 (4%)	400 (100%)
How effective are social media campaigns in addressing the following?	VE	E	U	I	VI	
a) Gender-based violence	100 (25%)	109 (27%)	37 (9%)	96 (24%)	58 (14%)	400 (100%)
b) Women's political participation	197 (49%)	134 (34%)	17 (4%)	26 (6%)	26 (6%)	400 (100%)
c) Economic empowerment for women	87 (21%)	182 (45%)	24 (6%)	79 (20%)	28 (7%)	400 (100%)
d) Challenging cultural stereotypes	55 (14%)	198 (49%)	17 (4%)	76 (19%)	55 (14%)	400 (100%)
Do you believe online feminist campaigns translate into real-life change?	Often	Sometimes	Not Sure	Rarely	Never	
	88 (22%)	151 (36%)	95 (24%)	56 (14%)	10 (2%)	400 (100%)

Note: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, U = Undecided, D = Disagreed and SD – Strongly Disagreed

VE = Very Effective, E = Effective, U = Undecided, I = Ineffective and VI = Very Ineffective

Source: Field work, 2025

The table above shows that majority of the respondents, representing 80% affirmed that social media has contributed to increasing awareness of gender equality issues. 52% of the respondents agreed that social media campaigns effectively address gender-based violence. 83% of the respondents agreed that social media campaigns effectively address women political participation. 66% of the respondents agreed that social media campaigns effectively address economic empowerment for women, while 63% of the respondents agreed that social media campaigns effectively address challenging cultural stereotypes. Also, Majority of the respondents believe that online feminist campaigns translate into real-life change.

The findings show that residents of Akure South Local Government believe social media has contributed to increasing awareness of gender equality issues. They perceive social media campaigns as effective in addressing gender-based violence, women's political participation, economic empowerment for women, and challenging cultural stereotypes. Additionally, respondents believe that online feminist campaigns translate into real-life change.

Table 3. Challenges and Strategies of Feminist Activism on Social Media

Option	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL
Challenges of feminist campaigns on social media						
Online harassment	157 (39%)	176 (44%)	-	69 (17%)	-	400 (100%)
Lack of engagement	30 (8%)	41 (10%)	-	120 (30%)	209 (52%)	400 (100%)
Digital illiteracy	67 (17%)	186 (46%)	-	72 (18%)	75 (19%)	400 (100%)
Internet inaccessibility	85 (21%)	85 (21%)	-	167 (42%)	63 (16%)	400 (100%)
Cultural resistance	172 (43%)	122 (30%)	40 (10%)	36 (9%)	30 (8%)	400 (100%)
Strategies that can make feminist activism more effective on social media						
	Frequency			Percentage		
Collaborating with influencers	108			27%		
Educating the public about gender equality	100			25%		
Using local languages in campaigns	131			33%		
Combining online and offline activism	60			15%		
Total	400			100%		

Note: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, U = Undecided, D = Disagreed and SD – Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field work, 2025

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The table above shows that majority (83%) of the respondents affirmed that online harassment is one of challenges feminist campaigns face on social media social media. 82% of the respondents rejected the proposition that lack of engagement is one of challenges feminist campaigns face on social media social media. 63% of the respondents affirmed that digital illiteracy is one of challenges feminist campaigns face on social media social media. Majority (58%) of the respondents disagreed that internet inaccessibility is one of challenges feminist campaigns face on social media, while 73% of the respondents affirmed that cultural resistance is one of challenges feminist campaigns face on social media social media.

On the strategies that can make feminist campaign more effective on social media, 27% of the respondents agreed on “Collaborating with influencers”, 25% of the respondents agreed on “Educating the public about gender equality”, 33% of the respondents agreed on “Using local languages in campaigns” and 15% of the respondents agreed on “Combining online and offline activism”.

The findings reveal that residents of Akure South Local Government affirm that online harassment, digital illiteracy, and cultural resistance are the major challenges feminist campaigns face on social media. However, they do not consider a lack of social media engagement or internet inaccessibility as significant challenges for feminist campaigns. Furthermore, residents

agree that collaborating with influencers, educating the public about gender equality, using local languages in campaigns, and combining online and offline activism are effective strategies for enhancing feminist activism on social media.

Conclusion

This study examined the role of social media in feminist activism and gender equality campaigns in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria. Findings show that residents primarily use Twitter and WhatsApp, encountering gender equality campaigns monthly and engaging with them mostly by liking posts. The study reveals that social media effectively raises awareness about gender equality issues and addresses key challenges such as gender-based violence, women's political participation, economic empowerment, and cultural stereotypes. Respondents believe that online campaigns translate into real-life change, highlighting their potential for tangible impact.

However, barriers such as online harassment, digital illiteracy, and cultural resistance were identified, while issues like internet inaccessibility and lack of engagement were not considered major challenges. To enhance effectiveness, respondents recommended collaborating with influencers, using local languages, educating the public, and integrating online and offline activism. Social media has proven to be a powerful tool for advancing feminist activism in Akure South. Addressing the

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identified challenges and implementing the suggested strategies will strengthen the impact of digital feminist campaigns in Nigeria and Africa.

Recommendation

This study recommends that:

1. The Nigeria government should incorporate digital literacy training into national education initiatives, prioritizing women's empowerment and enabling them to effectively engage with feminist campaigns.

2. Organisations and organisers of feminist campaign and movement should provide resources and support for feminist campaigns to incorporate local languages, ensuring that messages are accessible and culturally relevant to diverse populations.

3. Funds should be allocated for initiatives that combine online social media campaigns with offline activities, fostering tangible, real-world impact.

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